

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Determining *E. coli* Growth Kinetics Through Experimentation with a Sartorius Bioreactor System: A Quantitative Study

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Version: 1.0.1

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20130356>

Publication date: May 2026

Abstract

This paper presents an experimental study of *E. coli* TOP10 growth kinetics and lactic acid production using a Sartorius bench-top stirred bioreactor. A single batch culture was operated at 37 °C under non-aerated, oxygen-limited conditions with Lysogeny Broth as the medium. Over 130 minutes, cell growth, pH, and dissolved oxygen concentration were observed to evaluate bacterial behavior and acid production.

Optical density at 600 nm was converted to cell mass density, and pH measurements were used to estimate lactic acid concentration, assuming lactic acid was the main acidic species. Data showed increasing biomass, decreasing pH, and oxygen depletion. Linear regression of the exponential phase yielded an effective growth rate constant of approximately 0.0087 min^{-1} , corresponding to a doubling time of 79.7 minutes. Lactic acid production scaled nonlinearly with biomass, fitting a power-law index of 2.06. These results indicate that oxygen limitation reduced the apparent growth rate compared to aerobic *E. coli* culture, yet still allowed measurable acid accumulation.

Apparatus

The most important piece of the Sartorius Bioreactor experimental apparatus is a 1.5 liter borosilicate tabletop vessel, as seen in the disassembled state in Figure 1, along with the DCU and supply towers. The headplate of the bioreactor has multiple ports allowing the use of multiple sensor types. It is also fitted with two three-bladed disc impellers to ensure an even distribution of cells and medium inside the reactor and throughout experimentation. The impellers were maintained at 300 rpm (probes and stirrer motor assembly can be seen in Figure 2), a higher rpm could cause shearing of the *E. coli* (TOP10 strain) cells in medium. In addition, a sparging ring is connected to the bioreactor for instances where oxygen or air must be pumped into the vessel medium. The sensors for measuring temperature, pH, and oxygen concentrations can be specified as follows: platinum RTD, FermProbe, and Broadley James D100 OxyProbe. Absorbance throughout the experiment was measured by a VWR UV-1600 PC spectrophotometer. Samples were transferred into cuvettes (Figure 3) and measured in the spectrophotometer (Figure 4). In addition, a heating blanket was wrapped around the reaction vessel and connected to the Sartorius main computer system to maintain a setpoint temperature of 37 °C (Figure 5). The setpoint was increased in 3-degree increments from its baseline temperature up to 37 °C. This was done to prevent an immediate overshoot of the blanket temperature or any damage to the internal circuitry.

Figure 1. DCU tower and supply tower with Culture vessel disassembled

Figure 2. Stirrer motor, pH and dissolved oxygen probes and RTD in place

Figure 3. Cuvette

Figure 4. Sample from culture vessel being placed in spectrophotometer

Figure 5. Culture vessel with probes and heating blanket

The selected medium for containing the *E. coli* cells was a lysogeny broth (LB), as seen being stirred before inoculation (Figure 6). This medium was chosen due to its concentration of nutrients, which is vital for cell growth. For experiments utilizing the aerator, an anti-foaming agent, Sigma-Aldrich Antifoam 204, is added to the medium. The experiment did not involve any air or oxygen being pumped into the reactor vessel. The goal was to study how cell growth behaved after all the *E. coli* used the oxygen in LB, resulting in anaerobic conditions. Mistakenly, Antifoam 204, was added to the LB before experimentation began.

Figure 6. Lysogeny Broth (LB) being stirred

Data Collection Method

The bioreactor experiment was carried out over the course of 130 minutes. Sensor measurements and spectrophotometer readings were taken every 20 minutes, excluding the first three data points and last 2 data points. They were taken at ten-minute intervals to allow for more accurate curve-fitting during data analysis. Increasing the number of data points also makes clearer the stages of bacterial cell growth. The spectrophotometer was zeroed using a cuvette with sterile LB, so that increases in light absorbance can be attributed to cell growth. Absorbance readings were taken at 600 nanometer wavelength, or OD₆₀₀ (optical density) for short.

At the start of experimentation, about 900 milliliters of sterile LB was added to the bioreactor vessel. The impellers connected to the second Sartorius bioreactor computer were then turned on at 300 RPM. An electric heating blanket was wrapped tightly around the vessel using a Velcro strap. After wrapping, the heating blanket was then plugged into the first Sartorius computer. The blanket was slowly brought up to 37 °C by increasing the setpoint in °C increments. After the desired setpoint temperature was reached, an *E. coli* suspension culture was then poured into the vessel through an opening in the headplate. After pouring in the bacteria sample (inoculating) and replacing the headplate, a small plastic syringe was connected to the dip tube in the headplate and used to draw up an immediate initial sample of bacteria medium. To prevent contamination of the bacteria medium, the syringe was drawn up and then pushed down again, effectively rinsing out the interior of the dip tube. Temperature, pH, and O₂ concentrations were recorded in an MS Excel spreadsheet at the same time that the dip tube extraction was performed. A small volume of medium, about 4 milliliters, is poured into the cuvette. Excess medium inside the cuvette is returned to the vessel through an opening in the headplate. After measuring the absorbance of a cuvette sample, the liquid inside is dumped into a waste container reserved for biohazardous material. It should be noted that *E. coli* is associated with some health concerns. Even though *E. coli* TOP10 is a non-pathogenic lab strain, it is still classified as a “Biosafety Level 1 (BSL-1) organism. This means it poses minimal risk to healthy adults, but standard microbiological practices must be followed to avoid contamination or accidental exposure. Therefore, appropriate personal protective equipment such as gloves and a lab coat or apron should be worn when handling cultures. And in terms of preventative measures to be taken in regard to this risk, individuals experimenting with the bioreactor should wash their hands at the end of the lab session, prior to leaving the laboratory.

Data Analysis Method

Spectrophotometer readings of OD₆₀₀ were converted to cell density using a standard calibration, which assumes that an OD₆₀₀ of 1.0 corresponds to a cell density of 8 × 10⁸ cells/mL. This assumption is based on data provided by an online calculator from Agilent Technologies. Cell densities (in cells/mL) were then converted to cell mass densities (in g/L) using the estimated average mass of an *E. coli* cell, assumed to be 1 × 10⁻¹² g. All calculations were performed in Excel and an example of this process can be found in the Spectrophotometry and Cell Density portion of the sample calculations in section III of the attachments. The calculation of cell mass density (C_{bact} , in g/L) from OD₆₀₀ values using the following relationship:

$$C_{bact} = OD_{600} \times 8 \times 10^8 \frac{\text{cells}}{\text{mL}} \times 10^{-12} \frac{\text{g}}{\text{cell}} \times 10^3 \frac{\text{mL}}{\text{L}} \quad (\text{Equation 1.})$$

Using the pH measurements gathered over the course of the experiment, the lactic acid concentration produced by the *E. coli* cells was calculated. It was assumed that lactic acid was the only acidic species present in the medium. The observed decrease in pH was attributed to both lactic acid dissociation and the self-ionization of water.

To determine total lactic acid concentration ($C_{HA,added}$), the hydrogen ion contribution from water had to be calculated first:

$$y = K_w \cdot 10^{pH}$$

where $K_w = 1.0 \times 10^{-14}$. The remaining proton concentration attributable to lactic acid was then:

$$x = 10^{-pH} - y$$

Finally, the total lactic acid concentration was calculated using the acid dissociation equilibrium:

$$C_{HA,added} = x \left(1 + \frac{10^{-pH}}{K_a} \right) \quad (2)$$

where $K_a = 1.38 \times 10^{-4}$ for lactic acid. This yielded lactic acid concentration in molarity (mol/L), which was then converted to mM by multiplying by 10^3 .

To explore how acid production is related to bacterial growth, the relationship was modeled using a power-law equation of the form:

$$C_{HA,added} = \alpha \cdot C_{bact}^n \quad (3)$$

Taking natural logarithms of both sides, the following is obtained:

$$\ln C_{HA,added} = n \ln C_{bact} + \ln \alpha \quad (4)$$

This linear form allowed us to determine the acid production scaling exponent n through regression of $\ln C_{HA,added}$ versus $\ln C_{bact}$. The slope of this plot represents n , and the y-intercept corresponds to $\ln \alpha$, the proportionality constant.

Sample calculations for this process are included in “Derivation of Acid Concentration Calculation” in Section III of the attachments. For future iterations of this experiment, it should be noted that the initial pH may require normalization to a value of 7 to avoid negative or non-physical concentration values early in the data set.

Another goal for this experiment was to see if the “doubling time” (time for number of cells to double from inoculation) could be estimated. Bacterial cell mass concentration follows exponential growth, modeled as:

$$C_{bact}(t) = C_{bact,0} \cdot e^{\mu t} \quad (5)$$

where C_{bact} is the cell mass density at time t in g/L, $C_{bact,0}$ is the initial cell mass density at time $t = 0$ in g/L, μ is the effective exponential growth rate constant in min^{-1} , and t is time in minutes.

Taking the natural logarithm:

$$\ln C_{bact} = \mu t + \ln C_{bact,0} \quad (6)$$

This linear form was used to determine μ from a plot of $\ln C_{bact}$ vs. time. The doubling time was then calculated using:

$$t_d = \frac{\ln 2}{\mu} \quad (7)$$

Results and Discussion

The results of the bioreactor experiment confirm a positive relationship between cell growth and acid production. Table 1 contains tabulated experiment parameters such as pH and optical density (OD_{600}) readings over time as well as the calculated concentrations of bacteria (g/L) and lactic acid (mM). Starting bacterial and lactic acid concentrations were 0.119 g/L and 5.60×10^{-5} mM, respectively. At the end of the 130 minute period, these values had increased to 0.280 g/L and 2.77×10^{-4} mM. The observed decrease in pH from 6.88 to 6.51 can be attributed to the accumulation and ionization of lactic acid in the LB.

Table 1. Measured values of pH and optical density (OD_{600}), along with calculated bacterial concentration (g/L) and lactic acid concentration (mM), as functions of time for *E. coli* TOP10 in a non-aerated bioreactor at 37°C.

Time (min)	pH	Optical Density (OD_{600})	Bacterial Concentration (g/L)	Lactic Acid Molar Concentration (mM)
0	6.88	0.149	0.119	5.60×10^{-5}
10	6.88	0.159	0.127	5.60×10^{-5}
20	6.87	0.164	0.131	6.08×10^{-5}
40	6.86	0.171	0.137	6.57×10^{-5}
60	6.81	0.195	0.156	9.04×10^{-5}
80	6.72	0.231	0.185	1.38×10^{-4}
100	6.61	0.288	0.230	2.05×10^{-4}
120	6.55	0.325	0.260	2.47×10^{-4}
130	6.51	0.350	0.280	2.77×10^{-4}

In a typical batch growth curve (plotted on a logarithmic scale), batch cell growth progresses through six phases: lag, acceleration, growth, decline, stationary, and death, as shown by Figure 10 in section I of the attachments. In the lag phase, cells adapt to the new environment and there is very little to no growth. Growth then starts in the acceleration phase and achieves its maximum rate in the growth phase. This is followed by the decline phase where growth slows due to either exhaustion of nutrients or a build-up of inhibitory products. Next, growth ceases in the stationary phase. Lastly, in the death phase, cells lose viability and lyse. Recognition of these phases is important for identifying the time range in which exponential growth occurs, which is necessary for calculating the exponential growth constant μ and the doubling time t_d .

Graphing the natural log of cell mass density data from table 1 against a normal time axis can help visually linearize the exponential relationship between time and density. The linearized cell growth equation is seen in equation 6 in the data analysis section. The slope of this equation is the exponential growth constant, μ , which was found through a linear fit to the data in figure 7. From 40 to 100 minutes, the natural log of cell mass density is mostly linear. MS Excel calculated the μ in this region to be about 0.0087 min^{-1} . From this value, the doubling time of *E. coli* in the system can be calculated as 79.7 minutes using equation 7. This is much higher than the documented doubling time of 15 to 20 minutes in ideal conditions (Widdel). With a typical t_d for *E. coli* being 20 minutes, its corresponding exponential growth constant would be around 0.0347 min^{-1} , under ideal conditions. It is likely that this ~300% difference can be attributed to the bioreactor not being aerated during operation. Without oxygen or air being bubbled into the system, the *E. coli* cells will quickly consume all the dissolved oxygen in the LB. In the case of lactic acid production, this could be desirable despite the slower doubling time, as anaerobic conditions promote its formation, and that is one of the key focuses of this initial experiment.

Figure 7. Natural logarithm (ln) of cell mass density as a function of time for *E. coli* TOP10 in a non-aerated bioreactor at 37°C. A linear trendline is fitted to the exponential growth phase (from $t = 40$ to 100 min), with the equation and coefficient of determination (R^2) displayed on the chart.

The following graph (Figure 8) shows the recorded measurements of both the pH and dissolved oxygen content of the bioreactor plotted over the experiment time. The graph shows a steep decline in dissolved oxygen through the first 40-60 minutes of reacting, where it falls below 1.0% after the first hour and eventually reaches 0.0% by the 130-minute mark. This is accompanied by a steady decrease in pH followed by a sharper decline after 40 minutes. The trends visible in this figure are representative of oxygen-limited conditions in batch fermentation and are consistent with the transition from aerobic to anaerobic metabolism in *E. coli*.

During oxygen depletion, bacterial growth not stopping immediately is observable, as evidenced by the continued decrease in pH as well as the increase in bacterial concentration (Table 1). *E. coli* cells continue to multiply, eventually under anaerobic conditions. The rapid decline in dissolved oxygen during the first hour reflects aerobic

respiration in combination with high metabolic activity early in the growth period. As oxygen becomes limited, *E. coli* begins to shift toward anaerobic metabolism, primarily fermentation. The increase in lactic acid production seen in Table 1 corresponds to the increased decline in pH presented in Figure 8. This drop in pH, especially after 40 minutes, suggests that acid accumulation increases as fermentation progresses, even in the absence of oxygen.

Figure 8. Dissolved oxygen concentration (% saturation) and pH plotted as functions of time in a non-aerated reactor at 37°C containing *E. coli* (TOP10 strain).

The following figure presents the natural logarithm of lactic acid concentration (mM) plotted against the natural logarithm of cell mass density (g/L), allowing us to quantify the relationship between cell growth and acid production. Thus, it is determinable if there exists a relationship between the two, as well as what form it takes. By applying the power-law model shown by equation 5 in the data analysis section, this relation is able to be evaluated. From the linearized form of this correlation (Equation 6), a trendline was fitted to the transformed data. The slope of this line enables us to determine the lactic acid production scaling exponent, n . Furthermore, the y-intercept corresponds to $\ln(\alpha)$, which is the natural logarithm of the proportionality constant.

From performing linear regression on the log-log plot shown in Figure 9, n was determined to be 2.06. This indicates a second-order relationship between acid production and cell mass density. This result suggests that the generation of lactic acid increases more than proportionally with the accumulation of biomass, particularly under the oxygen-limited conditions of the experiment. These findings confirm the existence of consistent, nonlinear scaling behavior between cell growth and acid production, as investigated in this paper. They also tell us the connection does not take the form of a first-order relationship, or some other order for that matter.

Figure 9. Natural logarithm (ln) of lactic acid concentration (mM) as a function of the natural logarithm (ln) of cell mass density (g/L). The equation for the best-fit line and the coefficient of determination (R^2) are displayed on the chart.

Conclusions and Recommendations

This experiment found an important correlation between *E. coli* biomass increase and lactic acid generation in oxygen-limited circumstances, with a second-order scaling exponent of around 2.06. However, the effective growth rate constant ($\mu = 0.0087 \text{ min}^{-1}$) and doubling time ($t_d \approx 79.7 \text{ min}$) were much lower than published estimates for *E. coli* under optimum circumstances ($t_d \approx 20 \text{ min}$). This reduced growth rate is most likely owing to unfavorable circumstances such as a lack of aeration, the use of a general-purpose LB medium, possible strain restrictions, and the unintentional use of an anti-foaming agent in the absence of sparging.

Several changes should be made to future experiments to increase their accuracy and relevance. Primarily, it is advised to carry out parallel studies in aerated settings to determine how oxygen availability affects growth kinetics and lactic acid output. This will assist in establishing the trade-offs between aerobic and anaerobic metabolism in microbial production. Furthermore, the selection of culture medium and *E. coli* strain should be reconsidered. Testing alternate medium for high-density growth, as well as other *E. coli* strains renowned for quicker replication or increased metabolite production, might greatly improve performance. The experiment's runtime should also be prolonged beyond 130 minutes to see the whole bacterial growth curve, including the stationary and death phases, which are required for accurate long-term bioprocess modeling. Finally, increasing the sample frequency—particularly in the early period—to 5-to-10-minute intervals would allow for a more exact identification of the lag phase and the commencement of exponential development. This increased resolution will improve curve-fitting precision and boost the dependability of kinetic models utilized in future research.

These proposals attempt to produce more representative kinetic data and optimize the bench-scale system before scaling. In conclusion, while the present setup effectively established a nonlinear relationship between biomass and lactic acid production, the slower-than-expected increase emphasizes the need for better experimental design. Future research should concentrate on improving strain selection, culture medium, and processing conditions. With these improvements, researchers and institutions will be in a better position to confidently evaluate microbial production at pilot and industrial sizes.

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I. Figures

Figure 10. Typical batch growth curve (note log scale)

II. Tables

Table 2. Summary of batch cell growth

<i>Phase</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Specific growth rate</i>
Lag	Cells adapt to the new environment; no or very little growth	$\mu \approx 0$
Acceleration	Growth starts	$\mu < \mu_{\max}$
Growth	Growth achieves its maximum rate	$\mu \approx \mu_{\max}$
Decline	Growth slows due to nutrient exhaustion or build-up of inhibitory products	$\mu < \mu_{\max}$
Stationary	Growth ceases	$\mu = 0$
Death	Cells lose viability and lyse	$\mu < 0$

Table 3. Table presenting how cell number and time correlate

0 h	3 h	6 h	9 h	The time passed since the beginning of the experiment. For convenience, we here use multiples of the doubling time. Generally: t
1 cell	2 cells	4 cells	8 cells	The number of cells, after each division event (= appearance of a new generation). Generally: N
$= 2^0$ cell	$= 2^1$ cells	$= 2^2$ cells	$= 2^3$ cells	The same numbers of cells as above, but written in a manner that reveals the mathematical principle behind the increase of N . Generally: $N = 2^n$

III. Sample Calculations

Spectrophotometry and Cell Density

$$\frac{N^{sample}}{V^{sample}} = \text{Cell density}$$

$$\frac{N^{sample}}{V^{sample}} = \frac{N_0^{sample}}{V^{sample}} e^{\mu t}$$

$$\frac{N^{sample}}{V^{sample}} \sim OD \text{ optical density}$$

Conversion from OD₆₀₀ to Bacterial Concentration (cells/mL)

$$C_{cells} = (OD_{600}) \left(8 \times 10^8 \frac{\text{cells}}{\text{mL}} \right)$$

$$C_{cells} = (0.149) \left(8 \times 10^8 \frac{\text{cells}}{\text{mL}} \right)$$

$$C_{cells} = 1.19 \times 10^8 \frac{\text{cells}}{\text{mL}}$$

Conversion from Bacterial Concentration to Cell Mass Density (g/L)

$$C_{bact} = (C_{cells}) \left(10^{-12} \frac{\text{g}}{\text{cell}} \right) \left(10^3 \frac{\text{mL}}{\text{L}} \right)$$

$$C_{bact} = \left(1.19 \times 10^8 \frac{\text{cells}}{\text{mL}} \right) \left(10^{-12} \frac{\text{g}}{\text{cell}} \right) \left(10^3 \frac{\text{mL}}{\text{L}} \right)$$

$$C_{bact} = 0.119 \frac{\text{g}}{\text{L}}$$

OD₆₀₀: spectrophotometer reading at 600 nm

8 × 10⁸: cells per mL per OD unit

10⁻¹² $\frac{\text{g}}{\text{cell}}$: cell mass of *E. coli*

10³: conversion from per mL to per L

Bacterial Growth Kinetics

For starting with one cell

$$n = \frac{t}{t_d} \quad N = 2^{t/t_d}$$

For starting with N_0 cells

$$N = N_0 \cdot 2^{t/t_d}$$

t : time

t_d : doubling time

N : number of cells, after each division event (= appearance of a new generation)

$N = 2^n$: same number of cells as above, but written in a manner that reveals the mathematical principle behind the increase of N

Growth Kinetics Equation

$$N = N_0 e^{\mu t}$$

$$C_{bact} = C_{bact,0} e^{\mu t}$$

$$\ln C_{bact} = \mu t + \ln C_{bact,0}$$

$$\frac{\ln 2}{t_d} = \mu$$

$$\mu = \frac{0.693}{t_d}$$

$$t_d = \frac{0.693}{\mu}$$

$$t_d = \frac{0.693}{(0.0087 \text{ min}^{-1})}$$

$$t_d = 79.7 \text{ min}$$

μ : effective exponential growth rate constant

(μ is determined by performing linear regression on $\ln C_{bact}$ vs. *time*)

t_d : doubling time

Derivation of Acid Concentration Calculation

AH – stands for Lactic Acid

$$C_{HA,added} = C_{HA,added,0} + C_{HA,added,0}(t)$$

Some starting acid, cells make more during experiment

Acid Dissociation Equilibrium

$$K_a = \frac{C_{H^+}C_{A^-}}{C_{HA}} \quad pK_a \text{ for Lactic Acid} = 3.86$$

$$K_a = 10^{-3.86} = 1.38 \times 10^{-4}$$

Water Dissociation Equilibrium

$$K_W = C_{H^+}C_{OH^-} \quad \text{self-ionization constant for water } 1.0 \times 10^{-14}$$

Let x and y represent extents (in M) of Rxn (1) & (2)

$$C_{HA} = C_{HA,added} - x$$

$$C_{A^-} = x$$

$$C_{H^+} = x + y$$

$$C_{OH^-} = y$$

$$K_a = \frac{(x + y)x}{(C_{HA,added} - x)} \quad K_W = (x + y)(y)$$

$$x + y = C_{H^+} = 10^{-pH} \quad \text{so } y = K_W \times 10^{pH}$$

$$y = K_W \times 10^{pH}$$

$$x = (x + y) - y = 10^{-pH} - y$$

$$K_a = \frac{(x + y)x}{(C_{HA,added} - x)}$$

$$C_{HA,added} = x + \frac{(x + y)x}{K_a} = x \left(1 + \frac{10^{-pH}}{K_a} \right)$$

Lactic Acid Molar Concentration (mM)

$$y = K_w \times 10^{pH}$$

$$y = (1.0 \times 10^{-14}) \times 10^{(6.88)}$$

$$y = 7.59 \times 10^{-8}$$

$$x = 10^{-pH} - y$$

$$x = 10^{-(6.88)} - (7.59 \times 10^{-8})$$

$$x = 5.60 \times 10^{-8}$$

$$C_{HA,added} = x \left(1 + \frac{10^{-pH}}{K_a} \right)$$

$$C_{HA,added} = (5.60 \times 10^{-8}) \left(1 + \frac{10^{-(6.88)}}{(1.38 \times 10^{-4})} \right)$$

$$C_{HA,added} = 5.60 \times 10^{-8} M$$

$$C_{HA,added} = (5.60 \times 10^{-8} M) \left(10^3 \frac{mM}{M} \right)$$

$M: mol/L$

$mM: mmol/L = M \times 10^3$

Quantifying Relationship between Cell Growth and Acid Production

Log of $C_{HA,added}$ as a function of log (cell density)

$$C_{HA,added} = \alpha C_{bact}^n ?$$

$$so \ln C_{HA,added} = n \ln C_{bact} + \ln(\alpha)$$

n : lactic acid production scaling exponent

(n is determined by performing linear regression on the log-log plot of lactic acid concentration vs. cell mass density)

α : proportionality constant in the power-law relationship between lactic acid production and bacterial growth

From graph of \ln (cell mass density) against \ln (lactic acid concentration):

$$n = 2.06$$

Thus confirms a second-order relationship, meaning lactic acid production scales quadratically with bacterial growth

IV. References

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